

DIAGNOSTICS AND SURGICAL TACTICS IN TRAUMATIC INJURIES OF THE SPLEEN.

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Traumatic injuries of the spleen account for 15 to 35% of all injuries to abdominal organs. Methods of treating the spleen are still controversial, since the important role of this organ in the body's immunological defense has been proven recently. There are reports of severe infectious diseases, often with a fulminant course, in patients who have previously undergone splenectomy.

Research material. Over the past two years, we have observed 42 patients in the emergency surgery department of the multidisciplinary clinic of the Tashkent Medical Academy, including 26 (61.9%) men and 16 (38.1%) women aged 19 to 66 years. 85% of patients were aged 30 to 50 years. In 14 (33.3%) patients, the injuries were open, in 28 (66.6%) - closed. The clinical picture was often unclear, especially in case of combined trauma of the abdominal organs. All patients with closed injuries underwent a comprehensive examination (general blood and urine tests, ultrasound of the abdominal cavity, if necessary - plain fluoroscopy of the abdominal organs) during which the nature and size of the injury, the volume of blood loss were determined. Further tactics of patient management, as a rule, depended on the size of the hemoperitoneum. In unclear cases, diagnostic laparoscopy was performed in 12 (28.5%) patients to clarify the diagnosis. Currently, we adhere to the principles of organ-preserving operations for spleen ruptures. At the same time, it is not always possible to perform organ-preserving operations, since the proportion of severe injuries is quite high.

Research results. We believe that absolute indications for splenectomy are damage to the vessels of the splenic pedicle, crushing of the spleen, ruptures in the hilum area and persistent bleeding. Splenectomy was performed in 26 patients. In 9 cases, the removed splenic tissue was implanted into the greater omentum. In case of ruptures and small wound sizes, splenic wound suturing with tamponade with a part of the greater omentum on the feeding pedicle was performed in 6 patients, electrocoagulation of the wound surface was used in 8 patients and a hemostatic sponge was used in 2 patients.

Conclusion. If a closed splenic injury is suspected, ultrasound and diagnostic laparoscopy should be the diagnostic standard. Whenever possible, preference should be given to organ-preserving operations